

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

ARHGEF2

(Rho guanine nucleotide exchange factor 2)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	9181 / Q92974 / -
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD
TREAT-AD Authors	Vittorio Katis ¹ , William Bradshaw ¹ , Mia Callens ¹ , Paul Brennan ¹ and the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center
Therapeutic Area(s)	Alzheimer's disease
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Affiliations	¹ Centre for Medicines Discovery, University of Oxford, Oxford, United Kingdom

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Biochemical assays: ARHGEF2/RHOA GTP exchange assay

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target was identified through a gene set enrichment analysis (GSEA) of the TREAT-AD target risk scores. The gene is among the leading edge (i.e. top-scoring) genes from the significantly enriched "Innate Immune Response" GO term. Network pathway modeling along with patient
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pseudotime analysis also implicated this gene as a central node within the network and a protein whose expression changes in pseudotemporally early disease progression.

TRET-AD Target Risk Score: 2.92 (rank #5546, 77.8th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target’s general relevance to Alzheimer’s Disease, and is the sum of the target’s Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 2.92 out of 5 (rank #5546, 77.8th percentile). The individual score components include 1.06 of 3 for genetics, and 1.86 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of ARHGEF2 protein is significantly decreased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. ARHGEF2 is annotated to GO terms from 8 different biodomains, but primarily terms from the Structural Stabilization, Immune Response, Apoptosis, and Metal Binding and Homeostasis biological domains.

Overall	rank	pctl	GeneticsScore	OmicsScore
2.917	5546	77.79	1.056	1.862

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer’s Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points

show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of expression. These data indicate that ARHGEF2 is confidently expressed in oligodendrocytes, microglia, excitatory and inhibitory neurons, as well as endothelial cells within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

ARHGEF2 is a Rho guanine nucleotide exchange factor implicated in neuronal development. ARHGEF2 is primarily a neuronal expressed gene. Network modelling and pseudotime analyses of proteomic brain samples identified ARHGEF2 as a target whose abundance changes early in AD progression. Inhibition of ARHGEF2 activity is predicted to reduce amylogenesis and neuronal inflammation in AD brains. This TEP describes ARHGEF2 antibody validation, ARHGEF2 and RHOA protein production, structural determination of the ARHGEF2/RHOA complex, identification of small molecule fragment ligands of ARHGEF2/RHOA complex, and assay development for ARHGEF2 guanine nucleotide exchange activity.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Alzheimer's disease (AD), a type of neurodegenerative disorder, is often associated with the loss of synapses and dendritic spines. There is increasing evidence that RhoA GTPases play a role in neuronal degradation (1). Overactivation of RhoA is connected to the production of amyloid-beta, Tau hyperphosphorylation, and neuroinflammation (2). The Rho family of GTPases is activated by guanine nucleotide exchange factors (GEFs), which enable the exchange of GDP for GTP.

ARHGEF2, a Rho GEF, has been implicated in the development of cortical neurons. Mice without ARHGEF2 are viable but exhibit deficits in neuron migration. Specifically, the dA1 neuronal progenitors do not migrate to the correct location in the hindbrain (3, 4). Individuals with a homozygous mutation of ARHGEF2 develop intellectual disability and mild microencephalopathy (4).

ARHGEF2, a member of the Dbl family of GEFs, contains both a Dbl homology (DH) domain and a pleckstrin homology (PH) domain. It associates with microtubules by binding the dynein motor light chain DYNLT1 (5). Here, it is kept inactive through phosphorylation by PAK1 at the C-terminus (at S886), allowing binding to 14-3-3 proteins (6). Upon microtubule disassembly, ARHGEF2 relocates to the plasma membrane and activates Rho GTPases through GTP exchange. Alternatively, phosphorylation by MARK3 kinase at the N-terminus of ARHGEF2 (at S151) causes its release from microtubules in the absence of microtubule depolymerisation (7). Active Rho triggers the ROCK1/2 signalling pathway, which ultimately leads to the reorganization of the actin cytoskeleton, a prerequisite for cell polarity and migration (8).

ARHGEF2 is also necessary for long-range inhibitory signalling mediated by calcium for neuronal polarization (9). Phosphorylation of the N-terminus of ARHGEF2 (at T103) by CAMK1 (Calcium/calmodulin-dependent protein kinase 1) increases ARHGEF2 Rho GEF activity and allows neurons to develop single long axons by inhibiting the development of immature neurites.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Proteins Purified

- 1. ARHGEF2A-c052:** Encodes residues 209-577 (DH-PH domain). Contains an N-terminal 6His-TEV fusion. For protein production in *E. coli*. Protein used in assays.
- 2. ARHGEF2A-c055:** Encodes residues 209-448 (DH domain). Contains an N-terminal 6His-TEV fusion. For protein production in *E. coli*. Protein used in crystallography and assays.
- 3. RHOAA-c033:** Encodes full length RHOA (residues 1-193). Contains an N-terminal 6His-TEV fusion. For protein production in *E. coli*. Protein used in assays.

4. RHOAA-c034: Encodes residues 1-184. Contains an N-terminal 6His-TEV fusion. For protein production in *E. coli*. Protein used in crystallography and assays.

5. RHOAA-c035: Encodes residues 1-184. Contains an N-terminal 6His-TEV fusion and a C-terminal AviTag fusion. For protein production in *E. coli*. Can be biotinylated. Protein used in assays.

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

Figure 1. SDS-PAGE of gel filtration fractions of purified ARHGEF2 and RHOA proteins

Crystal Structures

1. ARHGEF2/RHOA complex (PDB: [8BNT](#)).

Figure 2. Structure of ARHGEF2 DH domain in complex with RHOA (1.4 Å; PDB: 8BNT). ARHGEF2 and RHOA are coloured grey and pink, respectively. The switch I and switch II loops of RHOA that contact ARHGEF2 are colored purple and green, respectively. RHOA is not bound to a nucleotide. A GDP molecule is placed in the nucleotide binding site for reference.

See **Additional information (section 2)** with details of crystallography.

The DH domain of ARHGEF2 was crystallized in complex with RHOA, which is the first high-resolution structure of ARHGEF2. The GEF interacts with the switch I and switch II loops of RHOA in a manner that is typical for DH domain-containing GEFs. The contact surface area between the two is 1335 Å². The nucleotide binding site of RHOA in the complex lacks GDP, and this site is accessible for compound soaking in the crystal form.

2. Fragment-bound ARHGEF2/RHOA structures.

Small GTPases are normally thought to be a difficult class of proteins to inhibit. This is due to the very high affinity they have with either the GTP substrate or the GDP product. When bound to a GEF protein, the guanine nucleotide affinity is greatly weakened (from picomolar to micromolar), facilitating the exchange reaction. An opportunity to inhibit RhoA with small molecules may arise when bound to ARHGEF2. With this in mind, we attempted to identify small molecule fragments bound within the RHOA nucleotide binding site when bound to ARHGEF2, through crystallography-based fragment screening.

From 872 crystals soaked with fragments, 696 usable data sets with sufficient resolution (<3Å) were obtained. Of these, 56 fragments with convincing density were observed bound to the complex (PDB: 7G80, 7G81, 7G82, 7G83, 7G84, 7G85, 7G86, 7G87, 7G88, 7G89, 7G8A, 7G8B, 7G8C, 7G8D, 7G8E, 7G8F, 7G8G, 7G8H, 7G8I, 7G8J, 7G8K, 7G8L, 7G8M, 7G8N, 7G8O, 7G8P, 7G8Q, 7G8R, 7G8S, 7G8T, 7G8U, 7G8V, 7G8W, 7G8X, 7G8Y, 7G8Z, 7G90, 7G91, 7G92, 7G93, 7G94, 7G95, 7G96, 7G97, 7G98, 7G99, 7G9A, 7G9B, 7G9C, 7G9D, 7G9E, 7G9F, 7G9G, 7G9H, 7G9I, 7G9J).

Figure 3. Space-filling model of the ARHGEF2/RHOA complex with bound fragments. ARHGEF2 and RHOA are coloured grey and pink, respectively.

Of interest were 11 fragments that bound within the nucleotide binding pocket, some of which formed contacts with both ARHGEF2 and RHOA. These fragment scaffolds may be developed into inhibitors that are selective for the ARHGEF2-bound form of RHOA.

11 fragments within GTP binding pocket

Figure 4. Fragments bound at the nucleotide binding pocket of RHOA. The binding pocket is free of nucleotide, with GDP placed for reference.

See **Additional information (section 3)** with details of fragment screening.

See **Additional information (section 4)** for list of compound hits and structures.

Biochemical Assay

1. Nucleotide exchange assay

An *in vitro* GTP exchange assay, using Bodipy-FL-GTP, was established to monitor the activity of ARHGEF2 to convert GDP-bound RHOA to a GTP-bound form. Upon binding to RHOA, Bodipy-FL-GTP shows an increase in fluorescence.

Figure 5. Setup of an *in vitro* nucleotide exchange assay to monitor ARHGEF2 activity

The assay was used initially to confirm the specificity of activity of the DH domain of ARHGEF2. The addition of the DH domain to RHOA resulted in an 8-fold increase in GTP exchange. In contrast, ARHGEF2 did not stimulate the GTP exchange rate of other the related RHO GTPases RAC1 and CDC42.

Use of a protein construct that contains both the PH and DH domains of ARHGEF2 only slightly increased the exchange activity. Thus, the PH domain is not necessary exchange activity.

Figure 6. ARHGEF2 is a RHOA-specific GEF that requires only the DH domain for activity. (A) The initial rate of fluorescence increase (GTP exchange) was measured when the DH domain of ARHGEF2 was incubated with the RHO GTPases RHOA, RAC1 and CDC42. (B) The GTPase activity of RHOA (initial rate) was measured with the addition of ARHGEF2 that contains either both the DH-PH domains or the DH domain alone.

See **Additional information (section 5)** with details of assay conditions.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further biological investigation of the role of BDH2 in AD

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

1. Protein expression constructs and protein purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

ARHGEF2A-c052 tagged: Encodes residues 209-577 (DH-PH domain). Contains an N-terminal 6His-TEV fusion. For protein production in E. coli. Protein used in assays.

Gene name	ARHGEF2
Uniprot ID	Q92974
Region	E209-E577

Description	Rho guanine nucleotide exchange factor 2. DH and PH domains.
Synonyms	Guanine nucleotide exchange factor H1 (GEF-H1), Microtubule-regulated Rho-GEF, Proliferating cell nucleolar antigen p40
Construct ID	ARHGEF2A-c052
Parental vector	pNIC28-Bsa4
Tag	N-terminal His6-TEV
Protein mass (with tag)	45840.9 Da
Extinction Coefficient with tag (M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)	31400

Protein sequence (with tag)	MHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMEMDEKDFAAADSWSLAVDSSFLQQHKKEVMKQQDVIYELIQTE LHHVRTLKIMTRLFRTGMLEELHLEPGVVQGLFPCVDELSDIHRFLSLLERRRQALCPGSTRNFVIHR LGDLLISQFSGPSAEQMCKTYSEFCSRHSKALKLYKELYARDKRFQFIRKRVTRPAVLKRHGVQECILLVT QRITKYPLISRILQSHSHGIEERQDLTTALGLVKELLSNVDEGIYQLEKGARLQEIYNRMDPRAQTPVPG KGPFGRELLRRKLIHDGCLLWKTATGRFKDVLVLLMTDVLVFLQEKDQKYIFPTLDKPSVVSLLQNLIVR DIANQEKGMFLISAAPPEMYEHTASRDDRSTWIRVIQQSVRTCPSRE
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Purified Protein	
SEC: ARHGEF2A-c052 (with tag)	
Intact Mass Deconvolution: ARHGEF2A-c052 (with tag)	
Observed Mass:	45839.6 Da
Protein yield:	17.5 mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	<i>E. Coli</i> : BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE
Expression medium	Terrific broth (TB) with 50 µg/ml kanamycin (kan). Starter cultures also included 34 µg/ml chloramphenicol (cm).
Transformation and storage	Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE, a phage-resistant variant of Rosetta 2 (MSD). Plate on LB-agar plates containing kan (50 µg/ml) and cm (34 µg/ml). Inoculate LB broth containing the same antibiotics with several colonies. After overnight incubation at 37°C, add glycerol to 15% (v/v) final volume, and store at -80°C.
Expression	Inoculate LB + kan + cm media for overnight growth at 37°C. Inoculate 1 L of TB + kan with 10 ml of the overnight culture. Grow cultures at 37°C with vigorous aeration in 2.5 L Tunair flasks until reaching an OD ₆₀₀ = 1.5 - 2. Shift the cultures to 18°C for 30 minutes before

	inducing protein expression with 0.3 mM IPTG. Continue incubation for 16 hours at 18°C before harvesting cells by centrifugation (3000g, 25 min, 4°C). Store pellets and -80°C until needed.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lysis buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 2. W30 Buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 30 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 3. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 300 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP. 4. SEC buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 5. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resuspend thawed pellet in lysis buffer (40 ml/L of original culture). Lyse cells by sonication on ice (20 min, 5 s on, 10 s off, 35% amplitude) with occasional stirring. 2. Centrifuge the lysate (25 min, 67000g, 4°C). Decant the supernatant. 3. Add 0.8 ml of Ni-sepharose beads to lysate in a 50-ml falcon tube. Mix by rotation for 1 hr in a cold room. 4. Spin lysate with Ni-sepharose beads (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant lysate and wash beads with 30 ml Lysis buffer. Repeat wash with 15 ml lysis buffer. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 5. Wash column with 5 ml W30. 6. Elute protein with 3x 3 ml EB. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay.
Purification step 2: Size-exclusion chromatography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Concentrate the protein to 1 ml using a centrifugal concentrator with the appropriate MWCO. 2. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 HR 16/60 column in SEC buffer at 1 ml/min. 3. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 10-20 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 4. Assess quality of protein by LC-MS intact mass analysis. 5. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.

ARHGEF2A-c052 cleaved: Encodes residues 209-577 (DH-PH domain). Contains an N-terminal 6His-TEV fusion. For protein production in E. coli. Protein used in assays.

Gene name	ARHGEF2
Uniprot ID	Q92974
Region	E209-E577

Description	Rho guanine nucleotide exchange factor 2. DH and PH domains.
Synonyms	Guanine nucleotide exchange factor H1 (GEF-H1), Microtubule-regulated Rho-GEF, Proliferating cell nucleolar antigen p40

Construct ID	ARHGEF2A-c052
Parental vector	pNIC28-Bsa4
Tag	N-terminal His6-TEV
Protein mass (with tag)	45840.9 Da
Protein mass (without tag)	43375.3 Da
Extinction Coefficient without tag (M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)	29910
Protein sequence (with tag)	MHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMEMDEKFAADSWSLAVDSSFLQQHKKEVMKQQDVIYELIQTE LHHVRTLKIMTRLFRTGMLEELHLEPGVVQGLFPCVDELSDIHRFLSQQLEERRRQALCPGSTRNFVIHR LGDLLISQFSGPSAEQMCKTYSEFCSRHSKALKLYKELYARDKRFQQFIRKVTTPAVLKRHGVQECILLVT QRITKYPLISRILQHSHGIEEERQDLTTALGLVKELLSNVDEGIYQLEKGARLQEIYNRMDPRAQTPVPG KGPFGREELLRRKLIHDGCLLWKTATGRFKDVLVLLMTDVLVFLQEKDQKYIFPTLDKPSVVSQNLIVR DIANQEKGMFLISAAPPEMYEVHTASRDDRSTWIRVIQQSVRTCPSRE
Protein sequence (without tag)	SMEMDEKFAADSWSLAVDSSFLQQHKKEVMKQQDVIYELIQTELHHVRTLKIMTRLFRTGMLEELH LEPGVVQGLFPCVDELSDIHRFLSQQLEERRRQALCPGSTRNFVIHRLGDLLISQFSGPSAEQMCKTYSE FCSRHSKALKLYKELYARDKRFQQFIRKVTTPAVLKRHGVQECILLVTQRITKYPLISRILQHSHGIEEERQ DLTTALGLVKELLSNVDEGIYQLEKGARLQEIYNRMDPRAQTPVPGKGPFGREELLRRKLIHDGCLLWKT ATGRFKDVLVLLMTDVLVFLQEKDQKYIFPTLDKPSVVSQNLIVRDIANQEKGMFLISAAPPEMYEVH TASRDDRSTWIRVIQQSVRTCPSRE

Intact Mass Deconvolution: ARHGEF2A-c052 (without tag)	
Observed Mass:	43373.9 Da
Protein yield:	12.5 mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	<i>E. Coli</i> : BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE
Expression medium	Terrific broth (TB) with 50 µg/ml kanamycin (kan). Starter cultures also included 34 µg/ml chloramphenicol (cm).
Transformation and storage	Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE, a phage-resistant variant of Rosetta 2 (MSD). Plate on LB-agar plates containing kan (50 µg/ml) and cm (34 µg/ml). Inoculate LB broth containing the same antibiotics with several colonies. After overnight incubation at 37°C, add glycerol to 15% (v/v) final volume, and store at -80°C.
Expression	Inoculate LB + kan + cm media for overnight growth at 37°C. Inoculate 1 L of TB + kan with 10 ml of the overnight culture. Grow cultures at 37°C with vigorous aeration in 2.5 L Tunair flasks until reaching an OD ₆₀₀ = 1.5 - 2. Shift the cultures to 18°C for 30 minutes before inducing protein expression with 0.3 mM IPTG. Continue incubation for 16 hours at 18°C before harvesting cells by centrifugation (3000g, 25 min, 4°C). Store pellets and -80°C until needed.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lysis buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 2. W30 Buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 30 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 3. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 300 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP. 4. SEC buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 5. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resuspend thawed pellet in lysis buffer (40 ml/L of original culture). Lyse cells by sonication on ice (20 min, 5 s on, 10 s off, 35% amplitude) with occasional stirring. 2. Centrifuge the lysate (25 min, 67000g, 4°C). Decant the supernatant. 3. Add 0.8 ml of Ni-sepharose beads to lysate in a 50-ml falcon tube. Mix by rotation for 1 hr in a cold room. 4. Spin lysate with Ni-sepharose beads (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant lysate and wash beads with 30 ml Lysis buffer. Repeat wash with 15 ml lysis buffer. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 5. Wash column with 5 ml W30.

	6. Elute protein with 3x 3 ml EB. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay.
Purification step 2: TEV cleavage and reverse IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add His-tagged TEV protease to the protein at a 1:20 mass ratio and dialyse in 1-2 litres of SEC buffer at 4°C overnight. 2. Pass the protein solution through a 0.8 ml Ni-Sepharose column equilibrated with SEC buffer and collect the eluant. Wash the beads successively with 3 ml each of Lysis, W30, and Elution buffer. Determine the fractions containing the cleaved protein by SDS-PAGE and pool. The protein should be in the flowthrough, lysis, or W30 wash fractions, while the His-tag and TEV protease should be present only in the elution fraction.
Purification step 3: Size-exclusion chromatography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Concentrate the protein to 1 ml using a centrifugal concentrator with the appropriate MWCO. 2. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 HR 16/60 column in SEC buffer at 1 ml/min. 3. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 10-20 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 4. Assess quality of protein by LC-MS intact mass analysis. 5. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.

ARHGEF2A-c055 cleaved: Encodes residues 209-448 (DH domain). Contains an N-terminal 6His-TEV fusion. For protein production in E. coli. Protein used in crystallography and assays.

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Uniprot ID	Q92974
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Description	Rho guanine nucleotide exchange factor 2. DH and PH domains.
Synonyms	Guanine nucleotide exchange factor H1 (GEF-H1), Microtubule-regulated Rho-GEF, Proliferating cell nucleolar antigen p40
Construct ID	ARHGEF2A-c055
Parental vector	pNIC28-Bsa4
Tag	N-terminal His6-TEV
Protein mass (with tag)	31064.7 Da
Protein mass (without tag)	28599.1 Da

Extinction Coefficient without tag ($M^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	15930
Protein sequence (with tag)	MHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMEMDEKDFAAADSWSLAVDSSFLQQHKKEVMKQQDVIYELIQTE LHHVRTLKIMTRLFRTGMLEELHLEPGVVQGLFPCVDELSDIHRFLSQQLEERRRQALCPGSTRNFVIHR LGDLLISQFSGPSAEQMCKTYSEFCSRHSKALKLYKELYARDKRFQQFIRKVTRPAVLKRHGVQECILLVT QRITKYPLISRILQSHGIEEERQDLTTALGLVKELLSNVDEGIYQLEKGARLQEIYNR
Protein sequence (without tag)	SMEMDEKDFAAADSWSLAVDSSFLQQHKKEVMKQQDVIYELIQTE LHHVRTLKIMTRLFRTGMLEELHLEPGVVQGLFPCVDELSDIHRFLSQQLEERRRQALCPGSTRNFVIHRLGDLLISQFSGPSAEQMCKTYSE FCSRHSKALKLYKELYARDKRFQQFIRKVTRPAVLKRHGVQECILLVTQRITKYPLISRILQSHGIEEERQ DLTTALGLVKELLSNVDEGIYQLEKGARLQEIYNR

Purified Protein	
SEC: ARHGEF2A-c055 (without tag)	
Intact Mass Deconvolution: ARHGEF2A-c055 (without tag)	
Observed Mass:	28599.2 Da
Protein yield:	23 mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	<i>E. Coli</i> : BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE

Expression medium	Terrific broth (TB) with 50 µg/ml kanamycin (kan). Starter cultures also included 34 µg/ml chloramphenicol (cm).
Transformation and storage	Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE, a phage-resistant variant of Rosetta 2 (MSD). Plate on LB-agar plates containing kan (50 µg/ml) and cm (34 µg/ml). Inoculate LB broth containing the same antibiotics with several colonies. After overnight incubation at 37°C, add glycerol to 15% (v/v) final volume, and store at -80°C.
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	5. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N ₂ , and store at -80°C.
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RHOAA-c033 tagged: Encodes full length RHOA (residues 1-193). Contains an N-terminal 6His-TEV fusion. For protein production in E. coli. Protein used in assays.

Gene name	RHOA
Uniprot ID	P61586
Region	M1-L193

Description	Small GTPase RhoA. Full length.
Synonyms	Transforming protein RhoA
Construct ID	RhoAA-c033
Parental vector	pNIC28-Bsa4
Tag	N-terminal His6-TEV
Protein mass (with tag)	24320.8 Da
Extinction Coefficient with tag (M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)	19940
Protein sequence (with tag)	MHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMAAIRKKLIVVGDGACGKTCLLIVFSKDQFPEVYVPTVFENYVADI EVDGKQVELALWDTAGQEDYDRLRPLSYPDTDVILMCFSIDSPDSLENIPEKWTPEVKHFCPNVPIILVG NKKDLRNDEHTRRELAKMKQEPVKPEEGRDMANRIGAFGYMECSAKTKDGVREVFEMATRAALQA RRGKKKSGCLVL

Purified Protein

SEC: RHOAA-c033 (with tag)	
Intact Mass Deconvolution: RHOAA-c033 (with tag)	
Observed Mass:	24320.2 Da
Protein yield:	32 mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	<i>E. Coli</i> : BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE
Expression medium	Terrific broth (TB) with 50 µg/ml kanamycin (kan). Starter cultures also included 34 µg/ml chloramphenicol (cm).
Transformation and storage	Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE, a phage-resistant variant of Rosetta 2 (MSD). Plate on LB-agar plates containing kan (50 µg/ml) and cm (34 µg/ml). Inoculate LB broth containing the same antibiotics with several colonies. After overnight incubation at 37°C, add glycerol to 15% (v/v) final volume, and store at -80°C.
Expression	Inoculate LB + kan + cm media for overnight growth at 37°C. Inoculate 1 L of TB + kan with 10 ml of the overnight culture. Grow cultures at 37°C with vigorous aeration in 2.5 L Tunair flasks until reaching an OD ₆₀₀ = 1.5 - 2. Shift the cultures to 18°C for 30 minutes before inducing protein expression with 0.3 mM IPTG. Continue incubation for 16 hours at 18°C before harvesting cells by centrifugation (3000g, 25 min, 4°C). Store pellets and -80°C until needed.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lysis buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 2. W30 Buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 30 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 3. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 300 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. SEC buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 5. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 0. Resuspend thawed pellet in lysis buffer (40 ml/L of original culture). Lyse cells by sonication on ice (20 min, 5 s on, 10 s off, 35% amplitude) with occasional stirring. 1. Centrifuge the lysate (25 min, 67000g, 4°C). Decant the supernatant. 2. Add 0.8 ml of Ni-sepharose beads to lysate in a 50-ml falcon tube. Mix by rotation for 1 hr in a cold room. 3. Spin lysate with Ni-sepharose beads (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant lysate and wash beads with 30 ml Lysis buffer. Repeat wash with 15 ml lysis buffer. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 4. Wash column with 5 ml W30. 5. Elute protein with 3x 3 ml EB. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay.
Purification step 2: Size-exclusion chromatography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Concentrate the protein to 1 ml using a centrifugal concentrator with the appropriate MWCO. 2. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 HR 16/60 column in SEC buffer at 1 ml/min. 3. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 10-20 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 4. Assess quality of protein by LC-MS intact mass analysis. 5. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.

RHOAA-c033 cleaved: Encodes full length RHOA (residues 1-193). Contains an N-terminal 6His-TEV fusion. For protein production in E. coli. Protein used in assays.

Gene name	RHOA
Uniprot ID	P61586
Region	M1-L193

Description	Small GTPase RhoA. Full length.
Synonyms	Transforming protein RhoA
Construct ID	RhoAA-c033
Parental vector	pNIC28-Bsa4
Tag	N-terminal His6-TEV
Protein mass (with tag)	24320.8 Da

Protein mass (without tag)	21855.2 Da
Extinction Coefficient without tag (M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)	18450
Protein sequence (with tag)	MHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMAAIRKKLVIVGDGACGKTCLLIVFSKDQFPEVYVPTVFENYVADIEVDGKQVELALWDTAGQEDYDRLRPLSYPDTDVILMCFSDSPDLENIPEKWTPVVKHFPCNPVPIILVGNKKDLRNDHEHTRRELAKMKQEPVKPEEGRDMANRIGAFGYMECSAKTKDGVREVFEMATRAALQARRGKKKSGCLVL
Protein sequence (without tag)	SMAAIRKKLVIVGDGACGKTCLLIVFSKDQFPEVYVPTVFENYVADIEVDGKQVELALWDTAGQEDYDRLRPLSYPDTDVILMCFSDSPDLENIPEKWTPVVKHFPCNPVPIILVGNKKDLRNDHEHTRRELAKMKQEPVKPEEGRDMANRIGAFGYMECSAKTKDGVREVFEMATRAALQARRGKKKSGCLVL

Purified Protein	
SEC: RHOAA-c033 (without tag)	
Intact Mass Deconvolution: RHOAA-c033 (without tag)	
Observed Mass:	21854.4 Da
Protein yield:	21.3 mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	<i>E. Coli</i> : BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE

Expression medium	Terrific broth (TB) with 50 µg/ml kanamycin (kan). Starter cultures also included 34 µg/ml chloramphenicol (cm).
Transformation and storage	Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE, a phage-resistant variant of Rosetta 2 (MSD). Plate on LB-agar plates containing kan (50 µg/ml) and cm (34 µg/ml). Inoculate LB broth containing the same antibiotics with several colonies. After overnight incubation at 37°C, add glycerol to 15% (v/v) final volume, and store at -80°C.
Expression	Inoculate LB + kan + cm media for overnight growth at 37°C. Inoculate 1 L of TB + kan with 10 ml of the overnight culture. Grow cultures at 37°C with vigorous aeration in 2.5 L Tunair flasks until reaching an OD ₆₀₀ = 1.5 - 2. Shift the cultures to 18°C for 30 minutes before inducing protein expression with 0.3 mM IPTG. Continue incubation for 16 hours at 18°C before harvesting cells by centrifugation (3000g, 25 min, 4°C). Store pellets and -80°C until needed.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lysis buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 2. W30 Buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 30 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 3. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 300 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP. 4. SEC buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 5. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resuspend thawed pellet in lysis buffer (40 ml/L of original culture). Lyse cells by sonication on ice (20 min, 5 s on, 10 s off, 35% amplitude) with occasional stirring. 2. Centrifuge the lysate (25 min, 67000g, 4°C). Decant the supernatant. 3. Add 0.8 ml of Ni-sepharose beads to lysate in a 50-ml falcon tube. Mix by rotation for 1 hr in a cold room. 4. Spin lysate with Ni-sepharose beads (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant lysate and wash beads with 30 ml Lysis buffer. Repeat wash with 15 ml lysis buffer. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 5. Wash column with 5 ml W30. 6. Elute protein with 3x 3 ml EB. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay.
Purification step 2: TEV cleavage and reverse IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add His-tagged TEV protease to the protein at a 1:20 mass ratio and dialyse in 1-2 litres of SEC buffer at 4°C overnight. 2. Pass the protein solution through a 0.8 ml Ni-Sepharose column equilibrated with SEC buffer and collect the eluant. Wash the beads successively with 3 ml each of Lysis, W30, and Elution buffer. Determine the fractions containing the cleaved protein by SDS-PAGE and pool. The protein should be in the flowthrough, lysis, or W30 wash fractions, while the His-tag and TEV protease should be present only in the elution fraction.
Purification step 3: Size-exclusion chromatography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Concentrate the protein to 1 ml using a centrifugal concentrator with the appropriate MWCO. 2. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 HR 16/60 column in SEC buffer at 1 ml/min. 3. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 10-20 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 4. Assess quality of protein by LC-MS intact mass analysis.

5. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N ₂ , and store at -80°C.

RHOAA-c034 tagged: Encodes residues 1-184. Contains an N-terminal 6His-TEV fusion. For protein production in E. coli. Protein used in crystallography and assays.

Gene name	RHOA
Uniprot ID	P61586
Region	M1-G184

Description	Small GTPase RhoA. Full length.
Synonyms	Transforming protein RhoA
Construct ID	RhoAA-c034
Parental vector	pNIC28-Bsa4
Tag	N-terminal His6-TEV
Protein mass (with tag)	23363.6 Da
Extinction Coefficient with tag (M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)	19940
Protein sequence (with tag)	MHHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMAAIRKKLVIVGDGACGKTCLLIVFSKDQFPEVYVPTVFENYVADI EVDGKQVELALWDTAGQEDYDRLRPLSYPTDVLMLCFSIDSPDSLENIPEKWTPEVKHFCPNVPIILVG NKKDLRNDEHTRRELAKMKQEPVKPEEGRDMANRIGAFGYMECSAKTKDGVREVFE MATRAALQA RRG

Purified Protein

SEC: RHOAA-c034 (with tag)	
Intact Mass Deconvolution: RHOAA-c034 (with tag)	
Observed Mass:	23362.7 Da
Protein yield:	28.5 mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	<i>E. Coli</i> : BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE
Expression medium	Terrific broth (TB) with 50 µg/ml kanamycin (kan). Starter cultures also included 34 µg/ml chloramphenicol (cm).
Transformation and storage	Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE, a phage-resistant variant of Rosetta 2 (MSD). Plate on LB-agar plates containing kan (50 µg/ml) and cm (34 µg/ml). Inoculate LB broth containing the same antibiotics with several colonies. After overnight incubation at 37°C, add glycerol to 15% (v/v) final volume, and store at -80°C.
Expression	Inoculate LB + kan + cm media for overnight growth at 37°C. Inoculate 1 L of TB + kan with 10 ml of the overnight culture. Grow cultures at 37°C with vigorous aeration in 2.5 L Tunair flasks until reaching an OD ₆₀₀ = 1.5 - 2. Shift the cultures to 18°C for 30 minutes before inducing protein expression with 0.3 mM IPTG. Continue incubation for 16 hours at 18°C before harvesting cells by centrifugation (3000g, 25 min, 4°C). Store pellets and -80°C until needed.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lysis buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP W30 Buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 30 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 300 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP. 4. SEC buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 5. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resuspend thawed pellet in lysis buffer (40 ml/L of original culture). Lyse cells by sonication on ice (20 min, 5 s on, 10 s off, 35% amplitude) with occasional stirring. 2. Centrifuge the lysate (25 min, 67000g, 4°C). Decant the supernatant. 3. Add 0.8 ml of Ni-sepharose beads to lysate in a 50-ml falcon tube. Mix by rotation for 1 hr in a cold room. 4. Spin lysate with Ni-sepharose beads (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant lysate and wash beads with 30 ml Lysis buffer. Repeat wash with 15 ml lysis buffer. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 5. Wash column with 5 ml W30. 6. Elute protein with 3x 3 ml EB. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay.
Purification step 2: Size-exclusion chromatography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Concentrate the protein to 1 ml using a centrifugal concentrator with the appropriate MWCO. 2. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 HR 16/60 column in SEC buffer at 1 ml/min. 3. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 10-20 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 4. Assess quality of protein by LC-MS intact mass analysis. 5. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.

RHOAA-c034 cleaved: Encodes residues 1-184. Contains an N-terminal 6His-TEV fusion. For protein production in E. coli. Protein used in crystallography and assays.

Gene name	RHOA
Uniprot ID	P61586
Region	M1-G184

Description	Small GTPase RhoA. Full length.
Synonyms	Transforming protein RhoA
Construct ID	RhoAA-c034
Parental vector	pNIC28-Bsa4
Tag	N-terminal His6-TEV
Protein mass (with tag)	23363.6 Da

Protein mass (without tag)	20898 Da
Extinction Coefficient without tag (M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)	18450
Protein sequence (with tag)	MHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMAAIRKKLVIVGDGACGKTCLLIVFSKDQFPEVYVPTVFENYVADIEVDGKQVELALWDTAGQEDYDRLRPLSYPDPTDVILMCFSDSPDLENIPKWTPEVKHFPCNPVPIILVGNKKDLRNDHTRRELAKMKQEPVKPEEGRDMANRIGAFGYMECSAKTKDGVREVFEMATRAALQARRG
Protein sequence (without tag)	SMAAIRKKLVIVGDGACGKTCLLIVFSKDQFPEVYVPTVFENYVADIEVDGKQVELALWDTAGQEDYDRLRPLSYPDPTDVILMCFSDSPDLENIPKWTPEVKHFPCNPVPIILVGNKKDLRNDHTRRELAKMKQEPVKPEEGRDMANRIGAFGYMECSAKTKDGVREVFEMATRAALQARRG

Purified Protein	
SEC: RHOAA-c034 (without tag)	
Intact Mass Deconvolution: RHOAA-c034 (without tag)	
Observed Mass:	20897.1 Da
Protein yield:	22.5 mg/L of culture

Expression and Purification Protocol	
Expression host	<i>E. Coli</i> : BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE

Expression medium	Terrific broth (TB) with 50 µg/ml kanamycin (kan). Starter cultures also included 34 µg/ml chloramphenicol (cm).
Transformation and storage	Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE, a phage-resistant variant of Rosetta 2 (MSD). Plate on LB-agar plates containing kan (50 µg/ml) and cm (34 µg/ml). Inoculate LB broth containing the same antibiotics with several colonies. After overnight incubation at 37°C, add glycerol to 15% (v/v) final volume, and store at -80°C.
Expression	Inoculate LB + kan + cm media for overnight growth at 37°C. Inoculate 1 L of TB + kan with 10 ml of the overnight culture. Grow cultures at 37°C with vigorous aeration in 2.5 L Tunair flasks until reaching an OD ₆₀₀ = 1.5 - 2. Shift the cultures to 18°C for 30 minutes before inducing protein expression with 0.3 mM IPTG. Continue incubation for 16 hours at 18°C before harvesting cells by centrifugation (3000g, 25 min, 4°C). Store pellets and -80°C until needed.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lysis buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 2. W30 Buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 30 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 3. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 300 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP. 4. SEC buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 5. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resuspend thawed pellet in lysis buffer (40 ml/L of original culture). Lyse cells by sonication on ice (20 min, 5 s on, 10 s off, 35% amplitude) with occasional stirring. 2. Centrifuge the lysate (25 min, 67000g, 4°C). Decant the supernatant. 3. Add 0.8 ml of Ni-sepharose beads to lysate in a 50-ml falcon tube. Mix by rotation for 1 hr in a cold room. 4. Spin lysate with Ni-sepharose beads (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant lysate and wash beads with 30 ml Lysis buffer. Repeat wash with 15 ml lysis buffer. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 5. Wash column with 5 ml W30. 6. Elute protein with 3x 3 ml EB. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay.
Purification step 2: TEV cleavage and reverse IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add His-tagged TEV protease to the protein at a 1:20 mass ratio and dialyse in 1-2 litres of SEC buffer at 4°C overnight. 2. Pass the protein solution through a 0.8 ml Ni-Sepharose column equilibrated with SEC buffer and collect the eluant. Wash the beads successively with 3 ml each of Lysis, W30, and Elution buffer. Determine the fractions containing the cleaved protein by SDS-PAGE and pool. The protein should be in the flowthrough, lysis, or W30 wash fractions, while the His-tag and TEV protease should be present only in the elution fraction.
Purification step 3: Size-exclusion chromatography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Concentrate the protein to 1 ml using a centrifugal concentrator with the appropriate MWCO. 2. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 HR 16/60 column in SEC buffer at 1 ml/min. 3. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 10-20 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 4. Assess quality of protein by LC-MS intact mass analysis.

5. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.

RHOAA-c035 cleaved: Encodes residues 1-184. Contains an N-terminal 6His-TEV fusion and a C-terminal AviTag fusion. For protein production in E. coli. Can be biotinylated. Protein used in assays.

Gene name	RHOA
Uniprot ID	P61586
Region	M1-G184

Description	Small GTPase RhoA. Full length.
Synonyms	Transforming protein RhoA
Construct ID	RhoAA-c035
Parental vector	pNIC28-Bsa4
Tag	N-terminal His6-TEV
Protein mass (with tag)	25754.2 Da
Protein mass (without tag and biotinylated)	23514.6 Da
Extinction Coefficient without tag (M⁻¹ cm⁻¹)	25440
Protein sequence (with tag)	MHHHHHSSGVDLGTENLYFQSMAAIRKKLVIVGDGACGKTCLLIVFSKDQFPEVYVPTVFENYVADIEVDGKQVELALWDTAGQEDYDRLRPLSYPD TDVILMCF SIDSPD SLENIPEKWTPEVKHFPCPNVPIILVGNKKDLRND EHTRRELAKMKQEPVKPEEGRDMANRIGAFGYMECSAKTKDGVREVFEMATRAALQARRGSSKGGYGLNDIFEAQKIEWHE
Protein sequence (without tag)	SMAAIRKKLVIVGDGACGKTCLLIVFSKDQFPEVYVPTVFENYVADIEVDGKQVELALWDTAGQEDYDRLRPLSYPD TDVILMCF SIDSPD SLENIPEKWTPEVKHFPCPNVPIILVGNKKDLRND EHTRRELAKMKQEPVKPEEGRDMANRIGAFGYMECSAKTKDGVREVFEMATRAALQARRGSSKGGYGLNDIFEAQKIEWHE

Purified Protein

<p>SEC: RHOAA-c035 (without tag and biotinylated)</p>	
<p>Intact Mass Deconvolution: RHOAA-c035 (without tag and biotinylated)</p>	
<p>Observed Mass:</p>	<p>23515.0 Da</p>
<p>Protein yield:</p>	<p>22.5 mg/L of culture</p>

<p>Expression and Purification Protocol</p>	
<p>Expression host</p>	<p><i>E. Coli</i>: BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE</p>
<p>Expression medium</p>	<p>Terrific broth (TB) with 50 µg/ml kanamycin (kan). Starter cultures also included 34 µg/ml chloramphenicol (cm).</p>
<p>Transformation and storage</p>	<p>Transform the construct into the <i>E. coli</i> strain BL21(DE3)-R3-pRARE, a phage-resistant variant of Rosetta 2 (MSD). Plate on LB-agar plates containing kan (50 µg/ml) and cm (34 µg/ml). Inoculate LB broth containing the same antibiotics with several colonies. After overnight incubation at 37°C, add glycerol to 15% (v/v) final volume, and store at -80°C.</p>
<p>Expression</p>	<p>Inoculate LB + kan + cm media for overnight growth at 37°C. Inoculate 1 L of TB + kan with 10 ml of the overnight culture. Grow cultures at 37°C with vigorous aeration in 2.5 L Tunair flasks until reaching an OD₆₀₀ = 1.5 - 2. Shift the cultures to 18°C for 30 minutes before inducing protein expression with 0.3 mM IPTG. Continue incubation for 16 hours at 18°C before harvesting cells by centrifugation (3000g, 25 min, 4°C). Store pellets and -80°C until needed.</p>
<p>Purification buffers</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Lysis buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 10 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP W30 Buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 30 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 300 mM imidazole, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP. 4. SEC buffer: 50 mM HEPES (pH 7.5), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 5. Ni-sepharose beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resuspend thawed pellet in lysis buffer (40 ml/L of original culture). Lyse cells by sonication on ice (20 min, 5 s on, 10 s off, 35% amplitude) with occasional stirring. 2. Centrifuge the lysate (25 min, 67000g, 4°C). Decant the supernatant. 3. Add 0.8 ml of Ni-sepharose beads to lysate in a 50-ml falcon tube. Mix by rotation for 1 hr in a cold room. 4. Spin lysate with Ni-sepharose beads (700g, 5 min, 4°C). Decant lysate and wash beads with 30 ml Lysis buffer. Repeat wash with 15 ml lysis buffer. Spin again and transfer beads to gravity column in a cold room. 5. Wash column with 5 ml W30. 6. Elute protein with 3x 3 ml EB. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay.
Purification step 2: TEV cleavage and reverse IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Add His-tagged TEV protease to the protein at a 1:20 mass ratio and dialyse in 1-2 litres of SEC buffer at 4°C overnight. 2. Pass the protein solution through a 0.8 ml Ni-Sepharose column equilibrated with SEC buffer and collect the eluant. Wash the beads successively with 3 ml each of Lysis, W30, and Elution buffer. Determine the fractions containing the cleaved protein by SDS-PAGE and pool. The protein should be in the flowthrough, lysis, or W30 wash fractions, while the His-tag and TEV protease should be present only in the elution fraction.
Purification step 3: Size-exclusion chromatography	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Concentrate the protein to 1 ml using a centrifugal concentrator with the appropriate MWCO. 2. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 HR 16/60 column in SEC buffer at 1 ml/min. 3. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 10-20 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. 4. Assess quality of protein by LC-MS intact mass analysis. 5. Snap-freeze aliquots in thin-walled PCR tubes in liquid N₂, and store at -80°C.

2. Crystallization of the ARHGEF2/RHOA complex and data collection

Prior to crystallography, the ARHGEF2/RHOA complex was formed and purified from monomeric species by SEC. ARHGEF2A-c055 was added to RHOAA-c034 in a 1:1.1 ratio and the complex purified on an S200 size exclusion column equilibrated with 50 mM HEPES pH 7.5, 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, and 1 mM TCEP. The fractions containing the complex were pooled and diluted 1:10 into buffer containing 10 mM HEPES pH 7.5, 150 mM NaCl, and 1 mM TCEP before re-concentrating to 7 mg/ml. Thin, needle-like crystals were obtained at 20°C when protein was added to reservoir solution containing 2.6M sodium formate, 0.1M Tris pH 8.5 in a 2:1 ratio. Mountable crystals took 4 days to 1 month to form. Cryoprotectant containing 4M sodium formate was added to the drops prior to loop-mounting crystals. All diffraction data were collected at Diamond Light Source. Data were processed using DIALS (10) and structures were solved by molecular replacement using the program PHASER (11). Crystals were in space group P4₃2₁2, with one copy each of ARHGEF2 and RHOA in the asymmetric unit. No nucleotide was observed in the nucleotide binding pocket of RHOA.

3. Crystallography-based fragment screening of the ARHGEF2/RHOA complex

Fragment screening was performed using the XChem pipeline at Diamond Light Source. Several hundred crystals were produced, as described above. Several crystals grown in these conditions were screened to confirm that the diffraction was routinely of a high quality and to a high resolution. Initial screening of DMSO soaked crystals showed a deterioration in diffraction quality from around 15-20% DMSO. Fragments from the DSI-posed (12), Covalent MiniFrag (13), and Cys electrophile (14) libraries were, therefore, soaked into crystals to a final DMSO concentration of 10% (giving a fragment concentration of 10-50 mM) using a Labcyte Echo (15) and allowed to incubate for between 2 and 5 hours. Crystals were fished from drops with the aid of a Shifter (16). Data were collected automatically on beamline I04-1 using X-ray centring and a rapid data collection protocol (0.1° oscillations, 3600 images). The resulting datasets were processed using XChem Explorer and PanDDA (17, 18).

4. List of compound hits and PDB files from the crystallography-based fragment screening

All compounds were purchased from SIA Enamine as powdered stocks and dissolved in DMSO to give 50-100 mM concentration.

Compound	SMILES	PDB
Z1041785508	<chem>c1csc(n1)c2nnc[nH]2</chem>	7G80
Z104474512	<chem>Cl.CCOc1cccc1N2CCNCC2</chem>	7G81
Z1079512010	<chem>Cc1cc(Cn2nc(C)ccc2=O)on1</chem>	7G82
Z108545814	<chem>CCC(=O)Nc1c(oc2cccc12)C(=O)N</chem>	7G83
Z1102357527	<chem>O=C(NC1CCC(=O)NC1)c2cscn2</chem>	7G84
Z111529496	<chem>COCC(=O)NCc1nc2cccc2[nH]1</chem>	7G85
Z1137725943	<chem>CCNCc1cccc2[nH]ccc12</chem>	7G86
Z1148165337	<chem>CN(C)C(=O)Cn1ncc2cccc12</chem>	7G87
Z1148747945	<chem>CC(=O)Nc1ccncc1C</chem>	7G88
Z1192341021	<chem>CC(=O)N1Cc2ccc(N)cc2C1</chem>	7G89
Z100642432	<chem>CN(C)C(=O)c1ccc(F)cc1Br</chem>	7G8A
Z100643660	<chem>CNC(=O)c1cn(C)c2cccc12</chem>	7G8B
Z1037511924	<chem>Nc1ccc2n(ccc2c1)C(F)F</chem>	7G8C
Z104474228	<chem>Cc1ccsc1C(=O)O</chem>	7G8D
Z104479710	<chem>Cl.Cl.NCc1nc2cccc2[nH]1</chem>	7G8E
Z1079168976	<chem>FC(F)(F)Cn1ccnc1CC#N</chem>	7G8F
Z111529496	<chem>COCC(=O)NCc1nc2cccc2[nH]1</chem>	7G8G
Z1198180782	<chem>COc1ccc2[nH]ccc2n1</chem>	7G8H
Z1198316457	<chem>NC(=O)C1CCC(F)(F)CC1</chem>	7G8I
Z1216861874	<chem>FC(F)Oc1ccc(=O)[nH]c1</chem>	7G8J
Z1217131798	<chem>Cc1nccn1c2ccnc2</chem>	7G8K
Z1251207602	<chem>Cc1nnc(s1)N2CCCCC2</chem>	7G8L
Z1255459547	<chem>CC(=O)Nc1cccc2cc[nH]c12</chem>	7G8M
Z1262549981	<chem>OC(=O)C1(CC1)Nc2cccc2</chem>	7G8N
Z1267800292	<chem>CNC(=O)c1cccc2cc[nH]c12</chem>	7G8O
Z1269184613	<chem>NS(=O)(=O)c1ccc2ncsc2c1</chem>	7G8P
Z1269220427	<chem>CS(=O)(=O)c1cccc2ccnc12</chem>	7G8Q
Z1270087714	<chem>CC1CN(CC(C)O1)c2nc(C)ns2</chem>	7G8R
Z1270393711	<chem>COc1cc(no1)C(=O)N</chem>	7G8S
Z1273312142	<chem>CCOc1c(F)cccc1C(=O)N(C)C</chem>	7G8T
Z131833926	<chem>CC1CCN(Cc2c[nH]c3cccc23)CC1</chem>	7G8U
Z133716556	<chem>CS(=O)(=O)NC1CCOc2cccc12</chem>	7G8V
Z1416193393	<chem>Cc1n[nH]cc1C2CCNCC2</chem>	7G8W
Z1416571195	<chem>NC(=O)c1ccnc(NC2CC=CC2)c1</chem>	7G8X
Z1449748885	<chem>Cl.COC1ccc(NC(=O)CN)cc1</chem>	7G8Y
Z1493056027	<chem>CS(=O)(=O)N1CCC[C@@H]1CN</chem>	7G8Z
Z1509195674	<chem>C1CNCC(C1)c2cccc3[nH]ccc23</chem>	7G90

Z1509257513	CNC(=O)C1CCCC2sc(C)nc12	7G91
Z1545313172	NC(=O)c1ccc(NC(=O)[C@@H]2CCCO2)cc1	7G92
Z1565771450	CC(=O)Nc1ccc(C)c2NCCCC12	7G93
Z1575337975	Fc1ccc(nc1)c2cc[nH]n2	7G94
Z165170770	CNC(=O)c1ccc(cc1)S(=O)(=O)N	7G95
Z1203730981	BrC1=NC=CN1	7G96
Z57899718	N#CC=1C=CC=CN1	7G97
Z4605084898	[I-].CN1C=C[N+](C)=C1Cl	7G98
PCM-0102102-001	Cc1oc(cc1)C2=NN(C(C2)c3occc3)C(=O)CCl	7G99
PCM-0102113-001	CNC(=O)c1cccc(NC(=O)CCl)c1	7G9A
PCM-0102116-001	Cc1cccc(NC(=O)CCl)c1	7G9B
PCM-0102141-001	CS(=O)(=O)c1cccc1NC(=O)CCl	7G9C
PCM-0102179-001	ClCC(=O)Nc1cccc(c1)N2CCCC2=O	7G9D
PCM-0102197-001	Cc1cc(NC(=O)CCl)on1	7G9E
PCM-0102209-001	ClCC(=O)Nc1cc2OCOc2cc1Cl	7G9F
PCM-0102236-001	COc1cccc1NC(=O)CCl	7G9G
PCM-0102245-001	NC(=O)C1CN(C(=O)CCl)c2cccc2O1	7G9H
PCM-0102253-001	Cc1cccc1CNC(=O)CCl	7G9I
PCM-0102281-001	Fc1cccc1S(=O)(=O)N2CCN(CC2)C(=O)CCl	7G9J

5. GTP exchange assay

The GTP exchange assays were performed in 20 µl reactions, using 384-well shallow-well microplates (PerkinElmer). ARHGEF2 and small GTPase proteins were diluted into assay buffer (20 mM Tris pH 7.5, 50 mM NaCl, 1 mM MgCl₂, 100 µg/mL BSA, 1 mM DTT) and mixed prior to dispensing 15 µl into wells. Plates were incubated at room temperature for 2 h to allow for complex formation. The exchange assay was initiated by the addition of 5 µl of bodipy-GTP (ThermoFisher; G12411). Final reactions contain 1 µM ARHGEF2, 62.5 nM small GTPase and 500 nM bodipy-GTP. Kinetics of bodipy-GTP binding to the small GTPases was measured by monitoring fluorescence at 520 nm every 30 s for 1 h. The experiments were performed in triplicate. The rate of fluorescence increase (fluorescence units /s) was calculated using GraphPad Prism. Error bars in bar charts denote standard deviation.

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